

Learning from Long-Term Care practices
for the European Care Strategy

The meanings of long-term care needs in Portugal

National report

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List of Acronyms

ADLs	Activities of Daily Living
ECCID	Home-based Teams of Continuous Care
EGA	Hospital Discharge Teams
ERPI	Residential Care Facilities for Older Persons
IADLs	Instrumental Activities of Daily Living
INE	National Statistics Office
LTC	Long-Term Care
RNCCI	National Network of Continuous Integrated Care
RRP	Recovery and Resilience Plan
SAD	Homecare for Older Persons
UC	Convalescence Unit
ULDM	Long Duration and Maintenance Unit
UMDR	Medium Duration and Rehabilitation Unit

Executive summary

The Portuguese Long-Term Care (LTC) system is a dual system that splits into two branches. One is the Social Care branch – *Respostas Sociais* (which would translate as “Social responses” but is generally labelled in the literature as Social Care) – while the other is the Healthcare branch – *Rede Nacional de Cuidados Continuados Integrados* (RNCCI), which translates into National Network of Integrated Continuous Care. Understandings of what is entailed in the concept of ‘care needs’ are deeply rooted in this dual system and definitions tend to mirror the duality of social care and healthcare.

The **needs for social care** involve identification of limitations in functionality that limit the possibility of living independently considering the context of life of the person, namely in terms of available material resources and family support. Contrary to social care needs, **healthcare needs** are understood as absolute and universal and to be tackled by the national healthcare system, which is a universal system.

Despite the fragmentation of the system across the healthcare and the social care institutional sectors, there is a growing consensus among stakeholders and researchers alike that borders are increasingly blurred and that higher levels of integration of the two types of needs are necessary to overcome performance problems of the LTC system, both on the healthcare and on the social care sides.

Understandings of needs are mirrored in how the topic is measured, monitored and regulated. In Portugal, the data and regulatory infrastructures related to LTC needs reflect the system fragmentation that separates social care needs from healthcare needs. If for the first there is scarcity of empirical evidence and administrative data, vagueness of assessment criteria and a regulatory framework that leaves ample space for arbitrary management on the care providers side, for the second there is not only a considerable wealth of data but also routine protocols of recording of data always offering up-to-date information and stricter regulatory frameworks.

The LTC system in Portugal displays traits of a highly centralised system in aspects of funding and regulation, coupled with traits of a very fragmented system at the level of service provision. This model applies, in broad terms, to both social care and healthcare LTC services. The State, through the national government and its constitutive bodies, finances the LTC system in Portugal. The social care system is funded directly by the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security, which involves a contributions-based financing model. The RNCCI system is funded jointly by the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security and by the Ministry of Health. The healthcare component is part of the National Health System and therefore funded by general taxation.

Discussion about future trends in needs for LTC point to both quantity and quality challenges.

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Introduction

This report is part of the European research project **LeTs-Care: Learning from Long-Term Care practices for the European care strategy**, a collaborative research project that engages and supports policy makers and other stakeholders in addressing the challenges posed by long-term care (LTC) across the European Union countries.

LeTs-Care brings together a consortium of seven European academic institutions, a unique European Network of Cities and Regions, and several social economy organisations operating in Austria, Denmark, Italy, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Spain. The project is coordinated by Ca' Foscari University of Venice, and in Portugal the research is conducted by University of Porto. The project started in April 2024 and will run until December 2027. It is funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe as stipulated in Contract 10113270.

Long-term care (LTC) systems across EU countries are facing important challenges and are trying to strike a balance between ensuring affordable, accessible and good quality care; high quality of work in the care sector and financial sustainability. According to the European Union's "care strategy", we should invest in practices that promote integrated and person-centred care to address these challenges.

However, to date, there is little systematic knowledge of the specific LTC challenges and of the meanings of, for instance, quality of care and quality of work in care across national and local contexts. In addition, we know that "good practices" are difficult to transfer or to extend because their outcomes are highly dependent on the context.

Furthermore, while "good practices" in care provision are frequently promoted across Europe, experience shows that their transferability is limited. What works effectively in one context may not yield the same results elsewhere, because outcomes are strongly shaped by local governance models, policy environments, available resources, and community networks. This complexity calls for a comparative, context-sensitive approach to the study of LTC systems — an approach that LeTs-Care aims to provide.

LeTs Care has three aims:

1. To provide a new, in-depth, reflexive understanding of LTC challenges across national and local contexts, for and with stakeholders and policy makers.
2. To understand how "integrative" and "innovative" practices work in context and to highlight the possibilities and limitations to their transfer.
3. To develop a new model for policy learning with and for stakeholders.

To achieve the first aim, the LeTs-Care team set out to understand the meanings of five structuring concepts within long-term care systems: *needs*; *care and quality of care*; *work and quality of work*; *sustainability*; and *inequalities*. Methodologically, LeTs-Care adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining the analysis of secondary data (including a review of national literature, both academic and grey literature, as well as policy documents) with the collection and analysis of primary data obtained through interviews with *stakeholders* and *policy makers* at national and subnational levels.

For each of the five key concepts, every national research team produced a dedicated report focusing on a contextualised understanding of its meaning within the respective long-term care system. The present document is one of these reports, forming part of the series of five national reports developed by the Portuguese research team within the framework of LeTs-Care. Specifically, this report focuses on the concept of long-term care needs in Portugal, examining how it is understood, articulated, and addressed within the national policy and care landscape. Equivalent

reports were produced by all research teams in the other participating countries. Building on the insights generated through these national analyses, the research consortium developed a comparative report that examines the five key concepts across the different national contexts, identifying convergences, contrasts, and shared challenges within European long-term care systems.

1. LTC Needs: definitions and history of a concept

The Portuguese Long-Term Care (LTC) system is a dual system that splits into two branches. One is the Social Care branch – *Respostas Sociais* (which would translate as “Social responses” but is generally labelled in the literature as Social Care) – while the other is the Healthcare branch – *Rede Nacional de Cuidados Continuados Integrados* (RNCCI), which translates into National Network of Integrated Continuous Care. Understandings of what is entailed in the concept of ‘care needs’ are deeply rooted in this dual system and definitions tend to mirror the duality of social care and healthcare.

There is no formal unified definition of LTC needs in Portugal. Definitions can be extrapolated from the contents of applicable legal diplomas and regulations, that define types of services, objectives of services and pricelists. Needs are more clearly defined under the healthcare branch, namely because they are tied to clinical conditions and operate as the basis of evaluation of the performance of the healthcare intervention. They are used primarily to define the type of healthcare needed by the service user. Under the social care branch, the definition of needs is more diffuse, with variations across providers, and more influenced by the framework of needs for assistance with activities of daily living (ADLs) and instrumental activities of daily living (IADLs).

Discourses of interviewed stakeholders and contents of policy documents and legislation point to:

- 1) An understanding of needs by **the regulator** that includes two main types of needs: needs for support that result from loss of autonomy for the independent realisation of activities of daily living and instrumental activities of daily living; and needs for specialised continuous healthcare that result from chronic health conditions and degenerative diseases. Needs are also considered in terms of severity of the limitations associated to the conditions that trigger needs, in view of establishing the level of support required.
- 2) At the level of **practices**, needs are defined and assessed in a dual manner, with the use of different instruments and protocols for the assessment of needs for social care – *necessidades de autocuidado* - and of needs for healthcare – *necessidades de cuidados de saúde*.

Reflecting the history of each of the two branches of the LTC system, needs are approached from either a social assistance and means-tested perspective (social care needs) or from a universal perspective as absolute needs (healthcare needs).

In the next sections we outline the understandings of LTC needs as phrased by stakeholders and as mirrored in policy documents, complemented by a dedicated section to outlining the conceptual definitions in use in the national scientific literature. As far as understandings of needs by stakeholders and in policy documents are concerned, we split our analysis into two types of LTC needs: social care needs and healthcare needs.

1.1. Social care needs

The **needs for social care** involve identification of limitations in functionality that limit the possibility of living independently considering the context of life of the person, namely in terms of available material resources and family support. This means that needs are defined with an eye on what type of social care service the person requires (need for home help, need for teleassistance, need for in-house institutional care, need for day-care) but not as an absolute need. Needs are calibrated according to whether the person can or cannot meet those needs by pooling his/her own resources.

Considering the three main services offered under the social care system, admission to the Home-Care Service (SAD – *Serviço de Apoio Domiciliário*), Day Centre (Centro de Dia) and Nursing Homes (ERPI – *Estrutura Residencial para Pessoas Idosas*) is based on standardised criteria that assess the older person's degree of dependence in ADLs and their social vulnerability. This vulnerability manifests itself in the limited availability or absence of a family support network, the risk of social isolation and in situations of social emergency (e.g. housing conditions considered of high risk; the older person is a victim of domestic violence, among others). However, the regulatory framework gives service providers a great deal of autonomy, allowing them to add specific admission criteria and establish their own weighting and scoring matrices. This discretion, while useful for adapting the criteria to the local reality, can create inequalities in access. There is a specific situation that is always included in cooperation agreements between the State and service providers funded by the State, that stipulates that all service providers have a certain number of places reserved for allocation directly by the Social Security services. Situations of social emergency are typically addressed by using this disposition and involve admissions where the care provider is not directly involved in the assessment of needs.

After admission, a more in-depth assessment of the older person's needs and expectations is carried out, with the aim of supporting the planning and organisation of the care services to be provided. This assessment process covers indicators of an objective nature - the economic situation of the older person and their household; housing conditions; health condition, including therapies and medication, and healthcare and rehabilitation needs; level of physical and functional capacity, considering bodily, sensory, motor, mental, cognitive and behavioural activities; habits, leisure activities and religiosity - and indicators of a more subjective nature - the older person's degree of satisfaction with their social relationships; the older person's representations of ageing, their life project in old age and their views of needs and expectations in relation to the services and professionals involved.

The needs assessment is carried out by the social services professionals. Table 1 below lists, in a summarised manner, the main criteria that are defined in applicable regulations to guide assessments of needs for different types of services. The contents of the table have involved the detailed analysis of technical documents that regulate the three main social care services for older persons in Portugal: homecare service; residential care service; daycentre. The criteria are the same for the three services. The table lists the details of the criteria recommended in Social Security manuals to guide professionals in determining eligibility and to manage admissions, with some interpretative additional notes from the authors. It must be highlighted that the criteria described in table 1 are not mandatory, but rather recommendations available in guidance manuals that were created with the goal of helping providers reach high levels of quality in service provision. Most of these guidance manuals were drafted almost twenty years ago and some argue they need revision.

Table 1. Criteria recommended in Social Security manuals to guide professionals in determining eligibility and to manage admissions in homecare, residential care and daycentre services

CRITERIA RECOMMENDED BY THE SOCIAL SECURITY SERVICES TO ASSESS NEEDS	INTERPRETATIVE NOTES OF AUTHORS
<p>Indicators to determine eligibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional capacity in ADLs and IADLs • Age (statutory age of retirement) • Lack of family or community support • Risk of social isolation • Situations of social emergency • Others 	<p>Criteria reflect a pro-poor approach that targets, in principle, those who have limitations in activities of normal life but that are simultaneously in a situation of economic and social vulnerability.</p> <p>When defining the criteria for ranking candidates, the service provider, in addition to considering the admissibility criteria set out in the manuals, can define a set of criteria that it considers appropriate within the framework of its mission, assigning them a weighting. Some examples of other criteria include place of residence of the person; the applicant is a user of other services of the organisation providing the service; match between expectations of the person and characteristics of the service provider.</p>
<p>Indicators to assess needs after admission and to organise individual care plans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composition of the household of the person • Socioeconomic situation of the person and his/her household members • Characteristics of the person's accommodation • Health status based on medical records • Functional capacities • Habits, interests and likes • Level of satisfaction of the person regarding his/her social networks • Views and expectations of the person about old age, his/her life project, the institution and the staff 	<p>Criteria combine aspects related to autonomy levels and health status with socioeconomic criteria, both types measurable by means of documental proofing. Subjective criteria related to preferences and views of the user are collected by means of interviews. Some aspects related to family relationships and behavioural aspects of the user can also be measured by means of observation by the professionals in charge of managing the service admission.</p>

Source: Institute of Social Security (s/d). *Manual de processos-chave – estrutura residencial para idosos*; Institute of Social Security (s/d). *Manual de processos-chave – serviço de apoio domiciliário*; Institute of Social Security (s/d). *Manual de processos-chave – centro de dia*.

1.2. Healthcare needs

Contrary to social care needs, healthcare needs are understood as absolute and universal and to be tackled by the national healthcare system, which is a universal system. Access to healthcare is defined as a right in applicable legislation, starting with the Constitution of the Republic in its article 64.^o (*Constituição da República Portuguesa*, 1976, updated in 1997). This broad framework sets the tone for understandings of LTC needs approached as healthcare needs.

The RNCCI aims to ensure, as stated in applicable legal diplomas, an integrated and continuous response to the combined needs of health care and social support of citizens. It is not, by definition,

focused on tackling needs of older persons, although in practice these constitute most users¹. Access to the network is based on two general criteria, namely that users must have: a) temporary or prolonged functional dependence that compromises the performance of activities of daily living; and b) clinical conditions that require the continuity of specialised healthcare, resulting from the after-effects of an episode of acute illness, geriatric syndrome, chronic illness, with frequent episodes of recurrence (e. g. chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, neurodegenerative disease, heart failure, diabetes), and severe, advanced or terminal illness. Healthcare offered under the RNCCI focuses on care needs geared towards rehabilitation, improving functionality, slowing down the progression of chronic conditions, preventive interventions of reablement or maintaining comfort and quality of life in terminal situations (palliative care). A recent reform of the system has separated the area of palliative care, that now operates as an independent system, although the RNCCI can still include support in palliative care. Some other changes have included the enlargement of the RNCCI to include a branch of mental healthcare, and a branch specialised in paediatrics LTC. In its current configuration the RNCCI includes three branches: the general network; the mental healthcare LTC network; and the paediatrics LTC network. (see a more detailed description of the system in the report on meanings of care).

Although the RNCCI also includes in its goals meeting the training needs of informal carers, guaranteeing continuity and quality of care in the home environment for the users of the services, this is not outlined as an admission criterion in the regulatory documents applicable. Some inconsistency in the description of admission criteria in official documents illustrates the difficulties in referrals reported by some interviewees.

Patient referral to long-term care needs to be clarified. There are many organisations in the country, many EGA's, so there are many referral channels. If this isn't clarified, I fear that we won't be using understandable referral rules. [...] And the lack of use of instruments, I'll come back to the instruments, none of this can be articulated without the use of an instrument which is the individual care plan. So people... and the individual care plan can't have three or four different names in the regulations. The individual care plan is an individual care plan. So it's multidisciplinary, it's where all the professionals who are involved in all of this insert what their planning is. [...]

So, in this context, I would say that the breadth of the criteria is greater than it was supposed to be because of the lack of an instrument. It's not because there's anything wrong with people, it's not because there's any intention, it's because there's a lack of concrete guidelines.

Interviewee code: DPN_1211

Within the framework of the RNCCI structure, the general network is the broadest area of intervention and includes the following types of care units: Convalescence Units (UC – *Unidades de Convalescença*); Medium Duration and Rehabilitation Units (UMDR – *Unidades de Média Duração e Reabilitação*); Long Duration and Maintenance Units (ULDM – *Unidades de Longa Duração e Manutenção*). The general network also includes Integrated Continued Home Care Teams (ECCID – *Equipas de Cuidados Continuados Integrados Domiciliários*).

¹ Reports on the annual activity of the RNCCI point to around 80% of users being over the age of 65, and around 50% being even over the age of 80 (Monitoring report of the RNCCI, 2023, available at https://www.acss.min-saude.pt/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/Relatorio-de-Monitorizacao-da-RNCCI-1-semester-2023_vf.pdf. Last accessed on the 17th of January 2025.

The following table (Table 2) summarises the specific criteria for admission to the above-mentioned units of the RNCCI general network. The criteria reveal understandings of needs to be tackled by the different services. Needs involve consideration of need for healthcare (in terms of intensity) provided by doctors and nurses; the complexity of the user's clinical condition; and the potential for improvement. There is an inverse relationship between the complexity and intensity of these criteria and the length of stay, in that the units with the shortest lengths of stay cater for users with more complex clinical conditions who require more intense and differentiated healthcare provision (measured in number of hours).

Table 2. Summary of the specific criteria of admission by type of service of the general network of the RNCCI

CRITERIA OF ADMISSION (CRITERIA USED FOR REFERRAL TO THE RNCCI) ⁽¹⁾	UC (STAYS UP TO 30 DAYS)	UMDR (STAYS FROM 30 TO 90 DAYS)	ULDM (STAYS OVER 90 AND UP TO 180 DAYS)	ECCID HOME-BASED CARE TEAMS
Potential for improvement of the patient	In the short term	In the short or medium term	In the medium and long term, or with no prospect of improvement	The need for care is associated with convalescence or terminal illness, which requires a degree of differentiation and intensity of care that exceeds the capacity of community-based primary healthcare units (local health centre). Patients are in a situation of dependency but have the housing conditions and informal support network to allow for long-term care to be provided at home.
Intensity of the needs for healthcare	Need for permanent nurse and medical care	Need for daily medical care and permanent nurse care	Need for regular medical care and permanent nurse care	
Complexity of the clinical condition	Care needs following acute illness (e.g. intensive rehabilitation; nasogastric tube feeding; treatment of bed sores or wounds; maintenance and treatment of starvation; continuous supervision of therapeutic administration; respiratory support measures; monitoring of chronic illness to prevent the risk of sudden worsening)	Care needs following acute illness or recurrence of acute illness (e.g. need for intensive rehabilitation; physical rehabilitation; prevention/treatment of bed sores; maintenance and treatment of starvation; respiratory support measures)	Care needs arising from stabilized acute and/or chronic illness and/or slowly progressing chronic illness and/or presence of geriatric syndrome	

⁽¹⁾ A person can be referred for more than one reason. Criteria are not mutually exclusive, but they do not need to be all present to justify the referral.

Source: *Unidade de Missão para os Cuidados Continuados Integrados* (2011); *Unidade de Gestão e Acompanhamento da Rede Nacional de Cuidados Continuados Integrados* (2024).

Although referral to the RNCCI involves the work of multidisciplinary teams that include at least one doctor, one nurse and one social worker (see more in section 3 on governance), there is evidence of healthcare needs taking the lead. The clear distinction between healthcare and social care needs is very visible in the discourses on interviewed stakeholders, with those that are closer to the RNCCI offering a narrower understanding of LTC needs as healthcare needs when asked about the national LTC challenges and provisions. This does not mean, however, that they are not aware of the risks of this dual approach to defining needs. Indeed, some were adamant about the inefficiencies of the LTC system when it is biased towards a biomedical understanding of needs and fails to embrace a more holistic perspective. Some stakeholders have emphasised the importance of including professionals with a more diversified set of competences in teams to help influence understandings of needs.

And then, when these people arrive in long-term care, some even, as I was saying, poorly referred, their circumstances don't always end with long-term care. There would have to be, I'm not saying a person's manager, nothing like that, but there would have to be a projection of the need for continuity. [The system] doesn't have this vision. And this, I think, doesn't just have to do with material resources, it has to do with a technical perspective of what multiple needs are. They're not just health, they're social, they're material, so it's a continuum of needs that leads us to design an appropriate response to each person's needs. It's people who are at the centre of needs and at the centre of the system.

Basically, not losing focus of what healthcare is, but giving it another colour. Do I make myself clear? We're biopsychosocial, not just bio, aren't we? And so we can add this greater dimension by enriching other professions. There are other professions that can enrich the response

Interviewee Code: DPD_1309

One important aspect that involves definition of care needs in the RNCCI is the fact that they are tied to funding rules and pricelists in the healthcare component. Additionally, in terms of financial return for the care providers, it is the healthcare component that represents a higher weight in the financials of institutions. This ends up pushing towards a high level of detail in how healthcare needs are assessed and contributes to the medicalisation of understandings of LTC needs.

In terms of provision there is a growing concern about the overlapping of healthcare needs and social care needs and a consensus around the idea that the social care sector is ill-equipped to tackle healthcare needs. This idea shows associated to arguments about the changes in profiles of users of LTC services, seen as increasingly older and with more complex health conditions that require regular and differentiated healthcare. At the same time, discourses emphasised the difficulties of collaboration between the healthcare and the social care system, seen as an obstacle to secure a more comprehensive response to the needs of those requiring LTC.

I think it's the lack of coordination between the health and social security areas. Because when we talk about care, we're not just talking about health care, we're talking about all the care that a person, especially an older person, needs. And I think that's the first challenge and it's a difficult political challenge to combat, so to speak.

Interviewee Code: PPN_1309

For many years now, I think there has been a pressing need to fundamentally reformulate the entire system of support for older persons, which is poorly structured, poorly disciplined and poorly functioning in relation to needs. And this has worsened in recent years for a very simple reason. The users are arriving at care homes at a much older age, much sicker, with serious chronic illnesses, more dependent, with dementia, but with a huge difference from 15 years ago. [...] Because Portugal doesn't have something that is common abroad, which is called nursing homes, and which we don't have, and which we should have. Now that it's expensive, it's much more expensive than the current situation [...].

This starts with a contradiction. Nursing homes aren't considered health facilities, but maybe they need to be, just like long-term care, for example, which also works badly, in quantity, completely insufficient for the needs...[...]

Because nursing homes with their current needs should have permanent nursing staff, maybe they should, but the ordinance doesn't say anything about that. Curiously, the ordinance and previous legislation, contrary to what many people think, do not oblige care homes to have a doctor. It obliges the home to provide whatever healthcare is necessary. But that's as simple as me calling the fire brigade to take a resident to the health centre to look after their health. Now, whether or not nursing homes need permanent nursing staff is a question. Whether or not they need a doctor is another matter.

Interviewee Code: DRN_1209

1.3. LTC needs as a concept in the scientific literature

The concept of needs identified in most of the articles analysed, for the period between 2014 and 2024, reflects the definition of dependency in the legal diplomas that created the RNCCI in 2006. In the 2006 Decree-Law n.º 101/2006 dependency is defined as *'the situation of a person who, due to lack or loss of physical, mental or intellectual autonomy, resulting from or aggravated by chronic illness, dementia, post-traumatic sequelae, disability, severe or incurable illness at an advanced stage, absence or scarcity of family or other support, is unable, on their own, to carry out the activities of daily living'* (Decreto-Lei n.º 101/2006).

In some national literature proceedings, the definition of LTC needs is deeply anchored in the reference to a condition of functional dependence of individuals as expressed in legal provisions (Barbosa et al., 2018; Martins et al, 2014; Pego & Nunes, 2018; Petronilho, 2014; Santana et al, 2014). Needs, however, are not explicitly defined as a concept, but rather defined in an implicit manner. In terms of empirical research, the assessment of care needs in samples of older persons is mainly based on the use of dependency scales such as the Barthel Index (Alves et al., 2020; Fonseca et al., 2023).

Some other research, on the other hand, tends to focus on health conditions to discuss needs and assess performance of the LTC system (Fonseca et al., 2023; Gonçalves-Pereira et al., 2024, Petronilho, 2016). In that sense, the literature largely reproduces the duality in understandings of LTC needs - social care needs and healthcare needs.

In general, authors approach needs by referring to the profile of the persons who need care: persons with special needs (Cruz-Cunha et al., 2015); persons suffering from chronic illnesses and/or disabilities (Cardoso et al, 2015); the "frail elderly", the "profoundly disabled" and/or the "severely ill" (Cardoso et al, 2015); persons dependent on self-care (Petronilho et al, 2014); sick persons (Figueiredo et al, 2014); older persons with high dependency or bedridden, with chronic illnesses

and/or acute illness (Petronilho, 2016); persons with chronic disabling illnesses (Petronilho, 2016); older persons with different levels of functional dependence, whether they are patients with multiple chronic pathologies or persons at an advanced stage of an incurable disease and at the end of their lives (Martins & Melo, 2016); persons in a situation of illness or dependence who require inter-sectoral and multi-professional responses (Ordem dos Enfermeiros – Secção Regional do Sul, 2014).

Needs are thematised as varying in intensity according to the individual's degree of dependence: in low dependence, individuals only need supervision in ADLs; in medium dependence, in addition to supervision, they need help to carry out some activities such as bathing, medication, among others; in high dependence, individuals need permanent and daily help, since they do not have the ability to fulfil their ADLs (e.g. people who are bedridden or cognitively impaired) (Figueiredo et al., 2014).

It is important to note that the concept of needs, although used in the literature about LTC, is not necessarily tied to LTC. Some authors discuss basic needs (e.g. food and hygiene) but also support needs to solve multidimensional problems (Barbosa et al, 2014). In that sense, the concept of needs is expanded to account for aspects related to the well-being of persons living at home/in the community and their carers (e.g. information on health services; 24-hour monitoring; personal hygiene; companionship; food/restaurants; personalised transport; appliance repair; personal care services; domestic services; information on shops; computer repair); housing needs; social relationships; meaningful activities; participation in the community and services (Correia et al., 2016; Cruz-Cunha et al., 2015).

Some authors take an explicit critical stance about how the concept of LTC needs is narrowly defined. They point out that the focus of definitions of needs is systematically on the physical health dimension, therefore neglecting other dimensions of needs such as those related to social relationships and social participation (Marcelino et al., 2018; Costa et al., 2024), material needs of access to goods and services (Aguar & Macário, 2017), needs concerning mobility and accessibility (Aguar & Macário, 2017) or needs associated to cognitive decline and dementia (Alves et al., 2024; Costa et al. 2015; Gonçalves-Pereira et al., 2024).

In some research, the subject to which the needs refer is extended to include the needs of carers, with an emphasis on informal carers. Meeting the needs of carers aims to improve their physical and emotional well-being, ensure better care for the person being cared for and reduce the burden of care work (Daveson et. al., 2014). Brandão et al. (2016) discuss respite care services in the context of informal care of persons with dementia. Other authors implicitly address the needs of carers for support from health professionals to train and develop care skills (Martins, et al., 2016); the need for support measures that value their work; and the need to increase partnerships between formal and informal carers (Martins et al., 2016).

2. Boundaries, differentiation and interrelations of meanings of needs

2.1. What needs fall under LTC needs?

Provision of LTC, in Portugal, rests on a clear distinction between healthcare needs and social care needs, which was at the very basis of how the LTC system was created and is currently organised.

Despite the fragmentation of the system across the healthcare and the social care institutional sectors, there is a growing consensus among stakeholders and researchers alike that borders are increasingly blurred and that higher levels of integration of the two types of needs are necessary to overcome performance problems of the LTC system, both on the healthcare and on the social care sides.

That's why, when I talk about continuity, it's not just treating circumstantial episodes of illness or greater illness, or greater severity of illness, but it's thinking that a very significant part of our older population, as well as needing healthcare, needs other types of care. And they are continuous. In fact, all of them are continuous. It's not in a section of their life that's already advanced post-hospitalisation, or due to health interference, but there are in fact many different needs here: health, yes, social, material and even a certain quality of lifestyle, even though they're getting on in life. So, I think this is a huge challenge.

Interviewee Code: DPL_1309

The topic is not new and was indeed at the basis of the creation of RNCCI. RNCCI was created to tackle the needs for LTC where the healthcare component is dominant and that could not be addressed by the traditional social care sector. RNCCI is regulated jointly by the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security, who share responsibilities also in terms of funding. Care provision under the RNCCI tackles both healthcare needs and social care needs, with each ministry responsible for funding each of those two components. Care units operate as second line hospitalization units for more complex cases from a clinical perspective, and as long-term stay units where rehabilitation and reablement are the main goals to allow for the transition to a more definitive LTC service (social care service) where needs for continuous support can be met.

The traditional social care network operates under the social assistance branch of the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security and tends to target needs for support associated to socioeconomic vulnerability and lack of alternative forms of support (family support).

Nowadays there is a growing concern about the increasing complexity of healthcare needs of persons using social care services, that are not prepared (and not funded) for delivering complex healthcare. The specific case of dementia is one of the most discussed by stakeholders. On the other hand, there are ongoing discussions about the needs for social care that are not met and that lead many patients to remain longer than they needed in hospital care facilities.

The change in the profile of users with new problems of dementia is forcing institutions to change their human resources ratios. In particular, those human resources that deal directly with the user. And these are

qualified resources - they have to be - which cost a lot of money. This will change the difference between the real cost and the technical cost.

Interviewee Code: ORN_2410

One of the consequences of the absence of a clear concept of LTC needs, including in the scientific literature, is that discourses, policies and academic debates often bring under the same hat aspects of need that are quite different in their origin and in how they can be tackled. There is an entire line of discussion that emphasises the multidimensional nature of needs - and their consequent complexity - integrating not only the dimension of care, but also others relating to the economic dimension, emotional and social well-being. For example, Marcelino et al. (2018), when discussing aspects of LTC, also point to the needs (of older people) for social inclusion and increased participation / contribution to society. This is just one example of an understanding of needs that offers a fuzzy picture about what LTC needs are and what falls and does not fall under LTC needs, all and all making it quite challenging to define priorities and establish boundaries.

2.2. LTC needs of whom?

Understandings of LTC needs from the perspective of whose needs are we talking about, can be summarised along three dimensions: clear cut divide between social care services for older persons and services for other groups, but with no support on formal definitions of age-specific needs; universal approach to healthcare needs and pro-poor means-tested approach to social care needs; emphasis on needs of care recipients and a more recent formal acknowledgement of needs of informal carers.

Social care needs are addressed based on a clear age split between social groups, that operates as well as a criterion for access to services. Under the social care system there is a dedicated branch to old age – *Respostas Sociais para Idosos* – that defines a menu of seven social care services to which only individuals over a certain age (typically the statutory age for retirement) can access. One could think this would come with a clear divide between how care needs of older persons and of persons with disabilities are formally understood, but that is not the case. Table 3 below displays the definitions of needs that are to be tackled by homecare services and residential care services for older persons and for persons with disabilities, as an example. It results clear that there is no understanding of needs as age specific but rather what seems to be the classic age segmentation of social protection systems that separates users based on shared assumptions about stages of the life course.

Table 3. Definitions of needs in applicable regulatory documents of selected social care services

SERVICE	DEFINITION IN THE SOCIAL CARE BRANCH FOR OLDER PERSONS	DEFINITION IN THE SOCIAL CARE BRANCH FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES
Home-care service	It is a service that involves the provision of care and services to families and/or individuals who are at home, in a situation of physical and/or psychological dependence and who are unable to temporarily or permanently fulfil their basic needs and/or carry out instrumental activities of daily living, nor do they have family support for this purpose.	It is a service that involves the provision of care and services to families and/or individuals who are at home, in a situation of physical and/or psychological dependence and who are unable to temporarily or permanently fulfil their basic needs and/or carry out instrumental activities of daily living, nor do they have family support for this purpose.
Residential care service	Collective accommodation, for temporary or permanent use, for older persons. It provides permanent services suited to the biopsychosocial problems of the older person, helps stimulate an active ageing process and creates conditions to preserve and encourage intra-family relationships and promote social integration.	Collective accommodation for persons with disabilities over the age of 16. It contributes to the well-being and improved quality of life of residents by promoting strategies to strengthen personal self-esteem and the ability to organise activities of daily living. It promotes or maintains residents' functionality and autonomy and facilitates integration into other structures, services or establishments more suited to the resident's life project. It promotes interaction with the family and the community.

Source: *Segurança Social Direta*, accessible at <https://www.seq-social.pt/inicio> (last accessed on the 15th of January 2025)

In a fast-ageing country² where there has been, historically, a high rate of poverty among older persons³, social care services have always been targeting those in a situation of socioeconomic vulnerability. Needs are always understood in context and given the socioeconomic and family situation of the person. There is a shared understanding of needs not being absolute and requiring weighting according to individual capacity to tackle them with own resources. The same does not apply to understandings about healthcare needs. Here, and as part of a definition of healthcare needs as grounded in the recognition of a universal right of access to healthcare, services are not stratified by age (i.e. age is not a criterion to determine access or type of care service) and access is based on the presence of a need without conditions or limitations determined by socioeconomic criteria or any other criteria besides the need itself. This is seen, by some stakeholders, as a source of distortion inside the system. Admission to the RNCCI does not involve any means-testing for the component of healthcare. The means-testing will only apply to the social care component of the services, but they are the smallest slice of the care provided and only applicable to some types of

² Census data for the last three decades shows the rate of growth of the older population in the country: the share of persons aged 65+ in the total population was 13,6% in 1991, 16,4% in 2001, 19,0% in 2011 and 23,4% in 2021 (Source: INE, Census 1991, 2001, 2011 and 2021. Available at <http://ine.pt>, last accessed on the 30th of January 2025).

³ Data from 2023, and according to official statistics, shows that the monetary poverty rate of persons over 65 was 21,1% (Source: INE, Statistics on Income and Living Conditions. Available at <http://ine.pt>, last accessed on the 30th of January 2025).

services that involve a more prolonged stay. Any person, irrespective of their income or family situation, will have access to the RNCCI if the clinical criteria for referral are met and at a very reasonable cost⁴. That person will most likely struggle to find an equivalent service in the social care sector and given the scarcity of available places the person may need to resort to a private-commercial solution, much more costly. Some stakeholders are critical about the distortion that stems from the dual approach to needs and that creates an incentive for persons to overstay in RNCCI units.

The other is that the so-called social cases, people who are discharged from hospital and stay in hospital, and in this case... I don't know if the Professor is aware that there is a rate of between 9% and 10% of admissions of social cases to hospital, but the long-term care network is 37%. The long-term care network is clogged up with social cases. These are people who have been discharged from the RNCCI and are still there. Either because they don't have a family or because the family refuses to pick up their relative. Anyway, a private home costs 1,500 euros per month, and in the worst case scenario, a person with a high income pays 500 euros to the long-term care network, in this case to the long-term care unit, to have their family member there. So it's a third of the cost, with a much higher quality of service than a residential care facility in the social care sector.

Interviewee code: DRN_1009

Discourses on needs and dispositions in policy documents are almost exclusively focused on the needs of those requiring care. Historically, Portugal has been an example of a family-based welfare state, with care provisions inside the family and by informal carers being seen as something natural. Discussions about the needs of family carers were mostly an issue for the academic debate. In the last decade, and especially with the constitution of civil society groups of representation of informal carers, the topic has gained visibility, and space has been opened for consideration of needs of informal carers. Stakeholders, though, consider that the attention paid to informal carers in terms of actual allocation of resources and availability of support services is insufficient.

Informal carers are a key player in the provision of care and in the overwhelming majority of situations they are the ones who provide the care, because most people are not institutionalised, they are at home. At most, they can benefit from home support services, but the informal carer must always be present. They have to be properly informed and trained, they have to be able to provide care. They need care themselves, because caring for someone is a very heavy task in physical terms, but often more so in psychological terms. The carer needs what is known as carer's rest, they need to maintain their social relationships, they may need psychological support, more or less intense, with whatever characteristics are needed at the time. Participation in mutual help groups and support groups is also important. And then there's the big challenge, which is how the informal carer, who is still of working age, manages to reconcile working life with caring.

Interviewee Code: PPN_1309

⁴ Hospitalisation in a Convalescence Unit or home care provided by the ECCI are free of charge for the user. For the other types of RNCCI in-patient care the social care component costs per user and per day are as follows, with the possibility of a Social Security contribution after means-testing: Medium Duration and Rehabilitation Unit €22.85; Long Duration and Maintenance Unit €11.34. (Source: Order no. 47/2024, issued on the 9th of February 2024).

3. Resources, Infrastructure, Regulation

Understandings of needs are mirrored in how the topic is measured, monitored and regulated. In Portugal, the data and regulatory infrastructures related to LTC needs reflect the system fragmentation that separates social care needs from healthcare needs. If for the first there is scarcity of empirical evidence and administrative data, vagueness of assessment criteria and a regulatory framework that leaves ample space for arbitrary management on the care providers side, for the second there is not only a considerable wealth of data but also routine protocols of recording of data always offering up-to-date information and stricter regulatory frameworks.

3.1. How are needs assessed?

Assessment of needs takes place in different ways depending on the type of LTC service or cash benefit the person is applying for and depending on who is responsible for the assessment. Below we list the description of applicable protocols of needs assessment for each service and cash benefit.

There are **three types of cash benefits** that fall under LTC: dependency benefit; carer's allowance; and social inclusion benefit. (See national report on meanings of care for more details on cash-for-care benefits).

The **dependency benefit** (*Complemento por Dependência*) involves submission of an application by eligible citizens⁵ that fill-in a form, in paper, that is submitted to the services of the Social Security Ministry. The form includes personal identification data, and identification of the type of care and support the person is receiving (and from whom). Entries in the form implicitly define a typology of eligible needs: help with household activities; help with bathing/showering and using the toilet; help with moving around in the house; help with preparation of food and feeding; living in a nursing home. There is an additional open category (others) where applicants may refer the diagnostics of dementia of the applicant, but that is not clearly explained. Nowhere else in the form is there any field for dementia, which is part of the criteria stipulated in applicable legal dispositions to determine the amount of the cash benefit the person will be entitled to. Applicants, or those acting on their behalf, are also asked to state if the person is bedridden or not. Needs are verified by the Social Security services staff and may be further assessed by medical staff if deemed appropriate. Two levels of needs are defined to determine amount of the cash benefit: 1st level needs, which involve limitations in ADLs and IADLs; 2nd level needs include the 1st level plus dementia and/or being bedridden. These levels are used to determine the amount of the cash benefit the person is eligible for. A further distinction is considered to determine that amount: whether the person is benefiting from a regular old-age pension (i.e. if the person has records of contributions to the Social Security) or if the person falls under the non-contributory branch (i.e. the person has no track record of contributions or has not reached the minimum amount of time of contributions to be eligible for a pension). The first get

⁵ Eligible persons include all persons receiving an old-age pension, a social pension or an invalidity pension. Moreover, persons with disabilities entitled to the Social Inclusion benefit can also apply for the dependency benefit. Persons diagnosed with specific diseases, stipulated in applicable regulations, can also benefit from this cash benefit (Familial Amyloidosis, Machado-José disease, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Multiple Sclerosis, Oncology, Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, rare diseases and others that lead to dependency). (Source: Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security online platform at <https://www.seg-social.pt/complemento-por-dependencia>, last accessed on the 30th of January 2025).

slightly higher amounts of money in each of the two levels of the dependency cash benefit. This is an additional element of fragmentation of the system in how it defines needs.

The **carer's allowance** (*Subsídio de Apoio ao Cuidador Informal Principal*) is one of the mechanisms of support to tackle informal carers' needs and part of a broader framework that defines the terms under which a person can be recognised as an informal carer. This involves a rather complex process from a bureaucratic perspective that is managed by the Social Security services, but if the applicant meets the conditions and is granted the status of informal carer, then the person becomes eligible for a series of mechanisms of support to address his/her needs as carer. One of those needs is the need for financial support by means of a carer's allowance. Regarding this cash benefit, the rules of eligibility involve means-testing at the household level (i.e. income of all members of the household is considered for determination of economic need). The reference value for eligibility is very low (in 2025 set at 574,75€ per month) and the amount to be paid to the informal carer is the difference between this reference and the computed individual income after applying a harmonisation formula. Being awarded the status of informal carer also leads to the definition, in collaboration with professionals from the healthcare sector and the social care sector, of a personal plan of support (*Plano de Intervenção Específico ao Cuidador*). It is here that we find a detailed list of needs of the informal carer that are evaluated: need for support and exchange of experiences with peers; needs for training and access to information; psychological and social support needs; need for carer's rest. The actual assessment of needs involves a rather discretionary exercise controlled by the public administration staff. Only the carer's allowance is subjected to a pre-defined algorithm.

The **social inclusion benefit** (*Prestação de Inclusão*) is a cash benefit paid to persons with disabilities. It is a benefit that is only eligible for those who have the disability formally recognised and does not include those for whom the onset of the disability took place after the age of 55. It is a cash benefit with a complex architecture that involves a flat-rate component and additional components dependent on means-testing and specific needs of support related to the type of disability. For this specific cash benefit there is no detailed reference to specific needs but rather a vague statement about the need to help compensate the disadvantages that come with disability and that may generate additional costs of living for the person and his/her family. Assessment of needs therefore does not involve any real assessment of needs but rather the validation of the level of functional incapacity and the analysis of own resources available.

Regarding the assessment of needs to determine eligibility and allocation of a place in a LTC service, different models apply to social care and to healthcare.

Needs assessment for **social care services** (*Respostas Sociais*) does not involve quantification of needs or any points system to determine severity of needs. Assessment is done using qualitative criteria that involve identification of limitations in ADL and IADL and information on material resources and social networks of support available (or not) for the person to tackle those needs on his/her own. Assessments follow criteria that are available in national manuals that offer a reference. The process, however, is managed directly by each provider (see Table 1 in section 1). The system incorporates therefore a high level of discretionary power in the hands of professionals acting as technical directors of service providers.

Needs assessment for **healthcare services** (*RNCCI*) involves a different protocol both in terms of who oversees the assessment and in terms of criteria used for the assessment (see Table 2 in section 1). Referral to the RNCCI is carried out by Discharge Management Teams (*Equipas de Gestão de Altas - EGA*), after hospitalisation, or by the Primary Health Care Referral Teams, located in the local healthcare centre, in the case of people living in the community or in an institution. In both cases, teams in charge of referral include healthcare professional and social workers. What is more important to highlight is that the referral is done by teams not involved in the direct provision of

the LTC service for which the person will be referred to. Assessment of needs involves a protocol of evaluation of clinical conditions that are defined with a relatively high level of detail in applicable regulations. Socioeconomic conditions are more loosely defined but still leave some room for discretion.

3.2. What evidence is collected about needs?

The topic of data collection and availability is once again a topic where the split between social care and healthcare comes into play.

Needs that are tackled by social care mechanisms that fall under the responsibility of the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security are harder to measure. Actual needs can at best be estimated from indicators of disability and declared need for support in national surveys or census collections run by the National Statistics Office (INE). Administrative data focus on uptake of services and therefore allows to measure needs that are met. Data on unmet needs is scarce. The table below lists indicators that can be used to compute needs for care in Portugal, identifying the source and periodicity of publication. We also include, for illustrative purposes, some of the last available data for each indicator.

Table 4. Available national indicators to measure LTC needs (last available data)

AVAILABLE INDICATORS	SOURCE ⁽¹⁾	PERIODICITY ⁽²⁾	DETAILS OF AVAILABLE DATA	ILLUSTRATIVE FIGURES (LAST AVAILABLE)
Incidence of functional limitations in the population by type and severity of the limitation	INE – Population census	Ten-yearly (last year available: 2021)	Limitations refer to sensorial, mobility, personal care, cognitive and communication functionality. Severity is classified in a 4 ranks scale (none, some, a lot, cannot do it).	A total of 110, 889 persons with full mobility impairment, 90% aged 65+ A total of 168,595 persons with full personal care impairment, 80% aged 65+
Population aged 16+ with declared limitations with activities dues to health problem (%)	INE – ICOR (Survey data)	Annual (last year available: 2023)	Limitations in performing activities are declared by the respondent. Limitations are classified in a 3 ranks scale (not at all; limited but not severely; severely limited)	A share of 7.6% of the total population aged 16+ declares severe limitations with activities due to a health problem. The figure is 15.8% among those aged 65+.

Table 4. Available national indicators to measure LTC needs (last available data) (cont.)

AVAILABLE INDICATORS	SOURCE ⁽¹⁾	PERIODICITY ⁽²⁾	DETAILS OF AVAILABLE DATA	ILLUSTRATIVE FIGURES (LAST AVAILABLE)
Population aged 55+ who reports difficulties with personal care, by type of personal care and by degree of difficulty	INE – INS (Survey data)	Five-yearly (last year available: 2019)	Difficulties with personal care are declared. Personal care type includes feeding oneself without help; lying down, sitting down or getting out of a bed or chair; dressing or undressing; using the toilet; bathing or showering; washing hands and face. Difficulty is measured with a 3 ranks scale: none; moderate; high.	A total of 544,183 persons aged 55+ have declared difficulties in at least one personal care activity. Of these, 11% declared they need help to perform the activity, which they are not getting.
Population aged 55+ who reports difficulties with household activities, by type of activity and degree of difficulty	INE – INS (Survey data)	Five-yearly (last year available: 2019)	Difficulties with household activities are declared. Household activities include preparing meals; using the telephone; shopping; managing medication; doing light housework; doing occasional heavy housework; and taking care of finances and administrative tasks. Difficulty is measured with a 3 ranks scale: none; moderate; and high, plus a 'never did it or needed to do' option.	A total of 1,473,911 persons aged 55+ have declared difficulties in at least one household activity. Of these, 26% declared they need help to perform the activity, which they are not getting.
Population aged 15+ providing informal care, by time spent weekly providing care	INE – INS (Survey data)	Five-yearly (last year available: 2019)	Time spent weekly providing care is measured in two classes of time: less than 10 hours; 10 or more hours.	1,059,012 persons aged 55+ declared providing informal care (12% of the total population). 43% of carers do it for 10+ hours per week.
Number of persons benefitting from a disability related pension	INE - ESSPROS	Annual/monthly (last available date: November 2024)	Double counting is accounted for since a person may be entitled to more than one disability cash benefit. In that case, the person is counted once.	155,839 persons in November 2024

Table 4. Available national indicators to measure LTC needs (last available data) (cont.)

AVAILABLE INDICATORS	SOURCE ⁽¹⁾	PERIODICITY ⁽²⁾	DETAILS OF AVAILABLE DATA	ILLUSTRATIVE FIGURES (LAST AVAILABLE)
Number of persons with the status of informal carer	SSD	Annual and monthly (last available date: November 2024)	Administrative data about applications for the status of informal care that had a positive result. Data is available cumulatively and per month. No data on total number of applicants.	9,879 primary carers and 6,274 non-primary carers. 5,721 primary carers receiving a carer's allowance.
Number of beneficiaries of the Social Inclusion Benefit (disability cash benefit), by level of disability	SSD	Annual and monthly (last available date: November 2024)	Level of disability is classified according to the International Classification of Disability (ICF).	160,006 persons receiving the cash-benefit.
Number of persons referred for admission in the RNCCI, by type of service	SNS - ACSS	Annual and monthly (last available date: December 2024)	Referrals include the ones done at the hospital and at the health centre. Referrals may be pending acceptance in the respective service	51,097 referrals during 2023 (annual report of the RNCCI): 11,052 for UC; 12,802 for UMDR; 10,270 for ULDM; 16,529 for ECCI.
Users waiting for a place in the RNCCI	SNS - ACSS	Annual and monthly (last available date: January 2025)	Users are referred and accepted for admission but are waiting for a place (waiting list).	2,108 persons waiting for a place on the 31 st of January 2025.
Number of users of old-age day centres	Carta Social – GEP/MTSSS	Annual (last available date: 2023)	Data available for the absolute number of users and for usage rate.	36,641 users representing a usage rate of 59%.
Number of users of home-care services for older persons	Carta Social – GEP/MTSSS	Annual (last available date: 2023)	Data available for the absolute number of users and for usage rate.	76,940 representing a usage rate of 65%.
Number of residents in nursing homes	Carta Social – GEP/MTSSS	Annual (last available date: 2023)	Data available for the absolute number of users and for usage rate.	99,356 residents representing an occupancy rate of 93% of available places.
Number of users in occupational services for persons with disability	Carta Social – GEP/MTSSS	Annual (last available date: 2023)	Data available for the absolute number of users and for usage rate.	12,405 users representing an occupancy rate of 93% of available places.

Table 4. Available national indicators to measure LTC needs (last available data) (cont.)

AVAILABLE INDICATORS	SOURCE ⁽¹⁾	PERIODICITY ⁽²⁾	DETAILS OF AVAILABLE DATA	ILLUSTRATIVE FIGURES (LAST AVAILABLE)
Number of residents in institutional care for persons with disability	Carta Social – GEP/MTSSS	Annual (last available date: 2023)	Data available for the absolute number of users and for usage rate.	6,869 residents representing an occupancy rate of 96% of available places.
Number of residents in autonomous residences for persons with disabilities	Carta Social – GEP/MTSSS	Annual (last available date: 2023)	Data available for the absolute number of users and for usage rate.	438 residents representing a usage rate of 98% of available places.
Number of persons using the Independent Living Support Service	Carta Social – GEP/MTSSS	Annual (last available date: 2023)	Data available for the absolute number of users and for usage rate.	816 users representing a usage rate of 63%.

⁽¹⁾ Acronyms used to identify sources of data are: ICOR (Survey on Income and Living Conditions), INS (National health Survey); ESSPROS (Statistics on Social Protection); SSD – Platform of the Social Security; SNS – National health System; ACSS – Central Administration of the Healthcare System;

⁽²⁾ Last available date at the date of production of the report.

There are anecdotal reports of long waiting lists for some specific types of LTC services, with nursing homes standing out in the media and in discourses of stakeholders as the service with longer waiting lists. There is no data supporting this statement since they are not collected. There is also irregular data on the number of persons that are hospitalised but that could be discharged if there was a place for them in the social care system. These cases are labelled as Social Hospital Stays (*Internamentos Sociais*) and are sometimes quantified in publications issued by the National Association of Hospital Administrators. This organization computes estimates, typically once a year, for this type of hospital stays based on data collected from a sample of hospitals at a given point in time.

[...] the insufficient number of infrastructures and inequities in accessibility to these infrastructures. The capacity of institutions such as nursing homes and day centres, which is limited, and public services or services with public agreements, which are often insufficient to meet demand.

Interviewee Code: DML_2012

aging families, who are the main providers of what is now called informal care, don't have the capacity if they don't have help in the community. Therefore, the pressure for hospitalisation is increasing and there is no installed capacity to respond.

Interviewee Code: ORN_2410

I can tell you that in a 60-bed unit like ours, I have 24 people who should be in a care home, and there are no vacancies.

Interviewee Code: ORN2_2410

4. Stakeholders and Governance

The LTC system in Portugal displays traits of a highly centralised system in aspects of funding and regulation, coupled with traits of a very fragmented system at the level of service provision. This model applies, in broad terms, to both social care and healthcare LTC services.

The State, through the national government and its constitutive bodies, finances the LTC system in Portugal. The social care system is funded directly by the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security, which involves a contributions-based financing model. The RNCCI system is funded jointly by the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security and by the Ministry of Health. The healthcare component is part of the National Health System and therefore funded by general taxation. Revenues from legal gambling are pooled to fund services under the rNCCI. The State also acts as regulator: it licenses services after verification of compliance with rules centrally defined; and it supervises operations of service providers to assess compliance with applicable rules. Provision of services is mostly secured by private entities: non-profit and for-profit. The first are the only ones with which the State can sign cooperation agreements under the social care system; under the RNCCI, the State will sign cooperation agreements with both non-profits and commercial entities.

Cooperation agreements define the terms of the transfer of funds from the State to service providers. In the social care system, payments are set at a fixed rate per user and per service. Co-payments by users may apply based on means-testing. In the RNCCI, the social care component is also funded at a fixed rate per user and per service. The healthcare component is funded according to the price list of healthcare services provided. The price list is also regulated centrally by the health authorities. There are no co-payments for the healthcare component.

Funding is only tied to needs assessment in the healthcare component of the RNCCI since transfers are defined by healthcare needs and concurrent healthcare provided. Funding of social care services is defined by broad type of service (nursing home, homecare, day centre, etc.), which partially implies different types of needs, but there is no person-centred assessment of needs with effects in terms of funding.

The process of licensing and supervision of operations of service providers in the social care system is fundamentally about verification of compliance with organisation of spaces, staff-ratios and compliance with administrative protocols. There is no supervision about level of adequacy or quality of provision in terms of satisfaction of needs of service users. In the RNCCI, largely as part of quality control protocols in place in the healthcare sector in general, there are instances of verification of levels of performance of service provision in meeting needs of users, and more transparent protocols of data collection on service provision.

Service providers, namely the ones that operate under contracts with the central State, retain a very high level of autonomy in operational aspects of service provision, including management of admissions. This means that the operational protocols of assessment of needs as well as the monitoring of evolution of needs of service applicants and service users is carried out by the service providers. The regulator (the State) issues some guidelines, but professionals in charge of managing services have a lot of discretionary power in assessing needs and deciding on admissions. This is a

peculiar aspect of the Portuguese system that is understood, by some stakeholders, as a source of distortion of the system in terms of ability to tackle the needs of those more in need. Some stakeholders suggest that some service providers, in the social care system, to secure their financial sustainability, resort to admitting older persons that can afford full payment of co-payment rates, and that may not be the ones who are more in need, rather than admitting applicants with a very low income and for whom co-payments will be set at a lower rate. There is a general perception in the population that placement in social care services is not solely based on needs but also on pressures from families, side payments, donations and other exchanges that take place outside the regulations.

[...] there is another serious problem in the care sector, which is corruption. And corruption sends people to illegal homes, it sends people to unsuitable homes, even legal ones, because there's nothing to stop this from happening. (...) Donations, and the most closely monitored donations, and donations to IPSS's are another problem. But the corruption is in referencing. In the social services themselves, in the hospitals, in the other services too, but the hospitals are where there are the most referrals, the operators are allowed to have contact with the social services. Referrals are made without telling anyone where the person went and how. Where did that person leave the hospital and go? And how? And by what route? Nobody knows. Well, the paper lists are manipulated. This is shameful. How can you talk about quality care when people are being referred to on the basis of interests? Corruption is also a problem, it's related to the quality of care.

Interviewee Code: MPN_0310

5. Territorial Differentiation

The system is very centralised in Portugal and the limited role of local municipalities in the formal governance of the LTC system does not create room for discussions on the specific needs of different regions. There is however some feedback about the implications of the characteristics of different territories in terms of the types of needs with an eye on sustaining claims about the necessity of having more flexibility in the system. Indeed, the topic that stands out in discourses from stakeholders regarding territorial differentiation of needs for LTC tends to emphasise the limitations of a highly standardised system, with some implicit criticisms targeting the regulator, that does not accommodate the specific characteristics of territories. Aspects regarding the distribution of the population with LTC needs, the topography of the territories where people with LTC needs are located, aspects of local cultures leading to preferences about how needs are to be tackled, are some of the topics that emerge both in the literature (Pereira, 2014; Correia et al., 2016; Barbosa et al., 2018, Marques da Costa & Barata, 2022; Nossa et al., 2024) and in discourses of stakeholders.

The South has fewer people, everything is more expensive, distances are much greater, people are much more isolated and this limits a standardised response at national level. So what's different has to be treated differently. That's obvious to me, what's different has to be treated differently and this need to highlight these territorial differences, if you don't do that, ends up creating a very large dissociation between populations.

Interviewee Code: ORN2_2410

Because there is indeed a different behaviour in the interior and in the big urban centres. There are many more homes on offer, it's true. There is also a sometimes supply of residential facilities, which still exists a lot in the big cities, and which people are already rejecting a little. So even though they are still small homes, they reject the fact that they don't have the facilities with the amenities and luxury and comfort that large facilities have.

Interviewee Code: MPN_0310

Indicators listed in table 4 (see section 3) are available with different levels of territorial differentiation, some by broad regions, others at the municipality and even at the local council levels. Trends in data seem to back up some understandings of the territorial distribution of needs found in the literature, in policy reports and in stakeholders' discourses.

Regarding the urban/rural divide, it is an important element but one that is not associated to variations in needs in a straightforward manner. If, on the one hand, it is highlighted the obstacles to meeting needs of populations that live in dispersed territories, in places that are sometimes hard-to-reach, and with living conditions that are often characterised by some material deprivation, on the other hand the high concentration of the population in urban areas is seen as a source of pressure in terms of size of demand for services. In fact, when analysing coverage rates of care services, the trend that emerges points to higher coverage rates in rural inland areas and to more pressure from the demand side in urban areas. The detailed data about the operations of the RNCCI leaves no doubt and puts the big metropolitan areas of Lisbon, Porto and Setúbal in the spotlight as the territories with the longest waiting lists and where there are more difficulties of admission in units close to the patient's home address.

We have identified, we have this question of the interior and the coast. Here we have the issue of that part of Portugal which is closer to the border, of isolation, of dispersion. The Alentejo is capable of travelling many kilometres to provide home care. It's capable of travelling 40, 50 kilometres to go to one person, then going to another point. [...]

It's not just in the interior, it's not in the deserted interior because there are still some community ties there, a sense of community humanisation that has been lost in the big centres. And that's where we're going to have the big problems, isn't it? What about the hospitals that can't empty their beds? The problem is that people aren't beds.

Interviewee Code: ORN_2410

Then there are others, which are the population centres. And then there's another kind of problem, which is that they're not so close together and the isolation ends up being greater, isn't it? So we've identified Porto, Lisbon and Setúbal. These are always the three worst districts. They have a lot of social problems, a lot of people on very low incomes, a lot of excluded people and it's very difficult to work there too. We also have a lot of problems with hospital discharges. [...] In other words, things are resolved elsewhere, but here it's really the three districts [...].

There are more blockages. There are many more problems. In other words, there are a lot of people... here, I'm thinking of Amadora. There are a lot of people on their own. When something happens to one of these people, there's nobody, there's no back-up.

Interviewee Code: DPN_0212

6. Debates and Strategies

Discussion about future trends point to both quantity and quality challenges. On the quantity side, there is an official recognition that the number of persons with needs for care and support is increasing, mostly associated to the ageing of the population. It is also recognised that Portugal has one of the lowest coverage rates in Europe so there is a sense of urgency due to the number of unmet needs. The LTC system is seen as needing significant growth to tackle growing needs. On the quality side, needs are also seen as becoming more diversified and complex. This is partially due to changes in preferences of individuals that are becoming more aware of their rights and more sensitive to aspects of quality of care.

The topic gained some additional steam in the last years as part of debates about the use of the funds available under the Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP). Unmet needs of older persons were largely disseminated in political discourses to support the use of those funds to reform and expand formal LTC services. In the next sections we outline the main findings on these issues.

6.1. Growing needs and strategies of expansion

Debates about the increase in care needs in contemporary societies, and specifically in Portugal, are approached within the context of population ageing and rising longevity. The increase in population longevity is understood as leading to an increase in the number of people with chronic diseases and multiple comorbidities, resulting in situations of dependency and need for care and support. Some authors explore in detail how demographic changes, characterised by population ageing and epidemiological changes, with the increase in the prevalence of disabling chronic diseases, pose challenges for healthcare organisation models (Petronilho, 2016; Pereira, 2014; Lopes, 2021). This is further explored as an element of pressure on the LTC system and discussed as one of the main reasons for the need to increase the supply of long-term care responses (Filipe et al, 2016). Santana et al (2014) also refer to changes in cultural patterns (a decline in the provision of informal care), along with demographic and epidemiological changes, as factors behind the sharp increase in demand for formal LTC.

Stakeholders agree with this general idea that needs have and are growing and that this growth pressures the LTC system.

It's not just our demographics, it's also what we know. And it will also evolve, according to what we already know, that there will be more and more of us who are older. And so we need to pay even more attention from that point of view. And we also know that when we compare ourselves to countries with the same life expectancy as ours, when we look at the Dalys, we know that we are in an even more unfavourable situation from a health point of view. That is, the last decade of life, the last decade and a half, is marked by enormous comorbidity. In other words, with many associated illnesses and, therefore, a low quality of life, with complex and multiple health problems. What our European colleagues have, therefore, is a much healthier life in this age group, in the last years of life. And so we not only have this factor working against us, but also the economic determinant I mentioned. So, all of this leads us to a more worrying dimension and a greater need to approach and prioritise what our needs are. That's why, when I talk about continuity, it's not just about treating circumstantial episodes of illness or greater illness, or greater severity of illness, but it's about thinking that a very significant part of our elderly population, as well as needing healthcare, needs

other types of care. And they are continuous. In fact, all of them are continuous. It's not in a section of their life that's already advanced post-hospitalisation, or due to health interference, but there are in fact many different needs here: health, yes, social, material and even a certain quality of lifestyle, even though they're getting on in life. So, I think this is a huge challenge.

Interviewee Code: DPL_1309

However, this apparent consensus is combined with some more critical understandings that discuss the accuracy of how public authorities and decision-makers are interpreting the growth of needs. This is related to recent policies that have defined as a target the expansion of the current 16,000 placements available in the RNCCI to an additional 5,500 in the general network, as set in the RRP contracts. Some stakeholders understand that the simple expansion of the number of beds without a detailed understanding of the reason why the current supply is considered insufficient is a negative development since it fails to tackle some of the underlying reasons for the accumulation of unmet needs. One of those reasons intersects territorial aspects, and the understanding is that expansion is not based on any accurate diagnostics of needs across different regions of the country and therefore may fail in correcting existing imbalances. One other reason concerns aspects of funding and availability of workers: some warn that expansion of number of beds is not sufficient to tackle unmet needs if additional measures regarding updating pricelists of services and creating conditions of attractiveness for the workforce in the sector are not considered.

(Interviewer) And how do you see the prospect of expansion now, even a very significant expansion of the network itself? Because with the PRR, with the investments in extending the network, there are going to be thousands more beds in long-term care, aren't there?

I'd just like to make one request, and that's that it shouldn't be done suddenly or at all costs. Because right now, in Portugal, we don't have the professionals to fill all these needs. We don't.[...] Now, we're just building ghettos. If we don't build dedicated functional teams with the required expertise, we're going to create ghettos. Basically, we're going to create corridors in which there is no exit door. That's it. It crystallises, crystallises and you lose fluidity. Fluidity is lost.

Interviewee Code: MPL_0310

So we're on our way and everyone's looking, and the way is in residential responses, isn't it? We're not going to be able to put everyone to bed, are we? As well as being able to explore a field of other types of responses here that hasn't been [explored].

Interviewee Code: DPN_0212

Well, as you know, in order to be moved out of your location, you have to have the person's consent, of course. And many people, when there is a vacancy, it's 100 kilometres away or 150, if it's an inpatient type. As I was saying, this is a problem that I don't think will be solved in the short term. It would only have a short-term solution if there was.... There's my tendency to evolve... If there was a political consensus, if the country decided. Because look, [...] there seems to be a general consensus. And then we should be able to evolve from that level of consensus to realising the idea. One of the implications is this, for example, perhaps, as

construction in Porto and Lisbon is more expensive, then the values should be different, or even create the discussion of public investment. But, as you understand, that's way beyond me.

Interviewee Code: DPN_1211

6.2. Diversification and quality

Needs for LTC are also approached in academic and political debates from the perspective of the increasing complexity and diversity of needs that the system must tackle.

Some authors highlight the expectation of increase in the demand for care and support, both in the social care and in the healthcare branches of the system, from older persons with different levels of functional dependence, with multiple chronic pathologies, and at an advanced stage of incurable diseases and at the end of their lives (Martins & Melo, 2016). This is discussed as a trait typical of contemporary trends that some discuss at the basis of what is perceived as a gap between the real needs of citizens and the way the system has developed. Some authors consider that there is a need for investment in the differentiation of care, in general, and in the management of chronic diseases, particularly in mental health (Costa et al., 2015, p.510). In a nutshell, there is consensus around the idea that there are differentiated needs that require differentiated care structures.

These arguments that are identified in the academic debate seem to echo in stakeholders' discourses, especially among those that are more engaged with the provision of services.

It's a growing problem. So, in our country, I think we're one of the oldest countries in Europe. And the forecast is that, even if the number of people here in Portugal decreases, by 2050 the target number of people with dementia is going to increase dramatically. It will almost reach 4 per cent of the population. Which is very frightening, because we don't have an adequate response today, we're unlikely to have one in 20 or 30 years' time.

Interviewee Code: DPN_0212

I'd also like to say that the institutions generally have a menu of services, the ones that respond, the ones that work with the elderly. The menu of responses, because that's the way it has to be, isn't it? Because there are users for whom what is best, most appropriate at the moment, is a day-centre. A parenthesis, an answer that is sadly in disuse. Regrettably. And which Social Security authorities don't encourage, and which would be a great way to promote active ageing.

Interviewee Code: ORN_2410

A more focused line of discussion concerns the debate about the needs of those who use services in residential care facilities. Pinheira and Beringuilho (2018) understand that residents in contemporary times require more intensive care and resources compared to the profile of needs of residents a decade ago. This is a common complaint voiced by stakeholders as well.

Discourses about future developments, in the academia and among stakeholders alike, are turning towards a more holistic approach to how and what needs must be tackled. Care needs are seen as requiring policies that go beyond the exclusive focus on care services to include a diversity of

sectorial policies. On the one hand, there is emphasis on the need to create conditions to lower the pressure from the demand side, in other words, to promote the decrease of needs. Promoting healthy ageing and investing in prevention are seen as promising paths (Lopes, 2021; Tavares et al., 2023). On the other hand, there is a consensual understanding that needs of care must be aligned with the principles of ageing in place, which requires consideration of housing issues (Szczygiel & Almeida, 2017), mobility issues (Aguiar & Macário, 2017; Fonseca, 2020) and implementation of desinstitutionalisation approaches (Lopes, 2021; Ferreira et al, 2019).

[...] what is the big strategy? This is the main point, it's not the only point, it's the main point for change. And there are a number of aspects here, a constellation of things that we're going to try to articulate so that these things can be orientated in a certain direction. And the aim is to give support, as much support as possible, so that people stay in their homes for as long as possible.

Interviewee Code: DPN_1211

Recent developments in the policy arena include the approval, in January 2024, of the National Plan of Action for Active and Healthy Ageing. This plan was drafted largely in response to the calls of the European Union, following the publication of the Green Book on Ageing, in 2021. A national coordinator of the plan was appointed and later included in the group of national LTC coordinators of the EU, as recommended by the Council Recommendation of 8 December 2022 on access to affordable high-quality long-term care 2022/C 476/01. The strategy never got traction in the media and was relatively confined to discussions in closed groups of experts and policy makers. Following the recent change in government, after the 2024 elections, the national coordinator for the area was fired by the new government and the national plan put on hold pending the elaboration of a national strategy for longevity. In the early days of 2025, the National Parliament resumed the topic and discussed proposals from different political parties to create a Chart of Rights for Older Persons. These proposals are based on claims about the specificity of needs of older persons, with care needs leading the list, but also on the recognition that it is not enough or adequate what has been done so far to tackle those needs. Debates are not very rich in contents and remain at a very general tone, especially because it is a topic that does not create clear cuts between political forces. The most significant divide concerns opposing views about whether needs should be met by direct public provision (supported by left-wing parties) or if they should be met in partnership with the private non-profit sector and holding families responsible for provision whenever possible (supported by right-wing parties).

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